

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. S. P. Singh, Department of Physics, R. B. S. College, Agra for providing necessary facilities for magnetic measurements.

References

1. O. F. WIEDE, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 3139.
2. K. A. HOFMANN and H. HIENDLMAIER, *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 3059; 1906, **39**, 3181.
3. E. H. RISENFELD, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 3941.
4. R. SCHWARZ and H. GIESE, *Ber.*, 1932, **65B**, 871.
5. R. C. RAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 68.
6. C. V. P. PILLAI and R. C. RAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 634.
7. B. S. RAJPUT, P. K. GOVIL and N. K. SINGHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 311.
8. D. R. SINGH, B. S. RAJPUT and O. P. KULSHRESTHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 838.
9. B. T. TJABBES, *Proc. Acad. Sci. Amsterdam*, 1933, **35**, 639.
10. W. KLEMM & J. WERTH, *Z. Anorg. Allgem. Chem.*, 1933, **216**, 127.
11. S. BHATNAGAR, B. PRAKASH and A. HAMID, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1428.
12. O. P. TOMAR, R. SINGH and J. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 209.
13. C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of I.R. Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963.
14. J. R. DYER, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice Hall Inc.
15. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and C. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identifications of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
16. SCHUMB, SATTARFIELD and WENTWORTH, "Hydrogen Peroxide", Reinhold Pub. Corp., New York, 1955.

Triazene-1-oxides. Part I. Cobalt(II) Mixed Chelates containing Triazene-1-oxide and Dipyriddy (or o-phenanthroline)

R. L. DUTTA & LEXHA DE

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan 713101, West Bengal

Manuscript received 27 January 1975; revised 25 April 1975; accepted 29 April 1975

SIGNIFICANT studies on the structures of square planar nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of triazene-1-oxides¹(I), formerly designated as 3-hydroxytriazenes²(II), have recently been done by Chakravorty *et al.*³. Tendency of adduct formation in pyridine is more pronounced in cobalt(II) (solution magnetic moment ~ 4.4 B.M.) than in nickel(II).

We report in this note some cobalt(II) pseudo octahedral complexes containing two triazene-1-oxide moieties and one dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline.

Experimental

The ligands were obtained following published procedures⁴.

General Method of syntheses of the mixed chelates: To an alcoholic (30 ml) solution of the ligand TH (X = H) (.002 mole) was added a solution of cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate (.001 mole in 30 ml 1:1 aqueous ethanol). The bis(triazenato-1-oxide) cobalt(II) complex was filtered, suspended in hot acetone (25 ml) and treated with dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline (.001 mole). The chocolate brown solution was filtered and the filtrate allowed to crystallise in a refrigerator. The deep chocolate brown crystals were of analytical purity but could be recrystallised from minimum volume of hot acetone. In the case of the nitroderivatives, the ligands (.002 mole) were dissolved in a greater volume of alcohol (~ 180 ml).

Estimation of cobalt and nitrogen and determination of conductance and magnetic moments were done as usual. Molecular weights were measured cryoscopically in benzene. Depressions being small (being limited by solubility of the complexes in benzene), the molecular weight values have a precision⁵ of $\pm 20\%$ of the calculated ones.

Relevant data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussions

The square planar bis(ligand) cobalt(II) complexes react readily with the N-N donor heterocycles, dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline to produce the mixed chelates $[\text{CoT}_2\text{dipy}]$ or $[\text{CoT}_2\text{o-phen}]$. The complexes are generally soluble in acetone, benzene, chloroform but less so in ethanol. The complexes are non-electrolytes, Λ_m in acetone⁶ being $\sim 1-26$ ohms⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹. Within limits of error ($\pm 20\%$) the complexes are also monomeric in freezing benzene. Since the 4-coordinated $[\text{CoT}_2]$ complexes were low spin square planar ($\mu \sim 2.1$ B.M.) it was fascinating to examine if the presence of the strong field dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline in the mixed chelates could produce low-spin pseudo-octahedral complexes. The

NOTES

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF COBALT(II) MIXED CHELATES

Complex	TH	Colour	M.P. °C	% Cobalt		% Nitrogen	
				Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = H	Brown	165—168	9.2	9.6	17.5	18.0
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = H	Brown	200—202	8.9	9.1	16.9	16.9
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = <i>p</i> -CH ₃	Dark brown	135	8.8	8.9	16.8	16.3
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = <i>p</i> -CH ₃	Dark brown	155	8.5	8.4	16.2	15.8
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = <i>m</i> -NO ₂	Dark red	132	8.1	8.5	19.2	18.7
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = <i>m</i> -NO ₂	Dark red	140	7.8	7.8	18.6	18.0
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂	Black red	220—223	8.1	8.8	19.2	19.9
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂	Black red	220—222	7.8	8.1	18.6	18.3

TABLE 2—CONDUCTIVITY, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF COBALT(II) MIXED CHELATES

Complex	TH	Molar conductance in acetone (ohms ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Room Temperature Magnetic Moment (B.M.)	Molecular weight in benzene			
				gm/100 g benzene	T (°C)	Found	Calc.
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = H	1	4.34	.159	.01	813	639
				.290	.02	743	639
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = H	5	4.73	.266	.025	548	663
				.266	.02	682	663
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = <i>p</i> -CH ₃	1	4.78	.309	.03	527	667
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = <i>p</i> -CH ₃	6	4.33	.312	.02	799	691
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = <i>m</i> -NO ₂	9	4.50	.233	.02	596	729
				.233	.015	794	729
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = <i>m</i> -NO ₂	26	4.36	.325	.02	832	753
[Co T ₂ .dipy]	X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂	7	4.43	.224	.02	575	729
				.224	.015	766	729
[Co T ₂ .o-phen]	X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂	11	4.41	.204	.015	695	753

present mixed chelates all produce high-spin values (4.3 to 4.7 B.M.), which is however below the lower limit of high-spin pseudo octahedral cobalt(II) complexes (4.7 to 5.2 B.M.)⁷. The low values may be indicative of a spin-state equilibrium between ⁴T_{1g} and ²E_g states (suggesting that the overall ligand field is close to the cross over region of 3d⁷ cobalt(II)). The high-spin values were expected to be corroborated by the ligand field transition ⁴T_{1g}(F) to ⁴T_{1g}(P) in the visible⁸. Unfortunately the ligand field bands were not well resolved. However, there is a suggestion of some structure around 520–580 nm.

References

1. T. MITSUHASHI, Y. OSAMURA and O. SHIMURA, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 2593.
2. B. BEHERA and P. S. ZACHARIAS, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1971, 27A, 2273.
3. D. N. PUROHIT, *Talanta*, 1967, 14, 353.
4. P. S. ZACHARIAS and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1972, 6, 623.
5. N. C. SOGANI and S. C. BHATTACHARYA, *Anal. Chim.*, 1956, 28, 81, 1616; 1957, 29, 397; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 563.
6. C. M. HARRIS, B. F. HOSKINS and R. L. MARTIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3728.
7. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1971, 7, 81.
8. R. L. CARLIN in "Transition Metal Chemistry" (Ed.), R. L. Carlin, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, Vol. 1, 1965, p. 1.
9. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1966, p. 871.